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Composing a New Score for Dovzhenko's *Earth* (1930): Practice-Based Research in Ukrainian Silent Cinema

A UKRAINIAN CINEMA MASTERPIECE BY OLEKSANDR DOVZHENKO

ZEMLYA

E A R T H

screening at

ACADEMY
MUSEUM
OF MOTION
PICTURES

JULY 23
2PM

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UFACE

ACCOMPANIED BY A LIVE PERFORMANCE OF THE NEW FILM SCORE BY
LUKE CORRADINE

Abstract

This paper examines the creation of a new musical score for Oleksandr Dovzhenko's *Earth* (1930), commissioned by the Academy Museum of Motion Pictures in 2023. The article discusses the compositional approach, the relationship between music and storytelling in the work, as well as the role of contemporary scoring in the revival of silent cinema.

Keywords

Ukrainian silent cinema; Oleksandr Dovzhenko; Earth (1930); film music composition; silent film scoring; film restoration; practice-based research

Introduction:

Oleksandr Dovzhenko's *Earth* (1930) is widely regarded as one of the most important works of early Ukrainian cinema and a landmark of Soviet silent film. As with many silent films, its performance history has been shaped by a limited number of musical interpretations accompanying restorations and official screenings.

This paper documents the creation of a new musical score commissioned by the Academy Museum of Motion Pictures and premiered at the Ted Mann Theatre of the Academy on 23 July 2023, alongside a newly restored digital version of the film.

It explores the compositional and analytical considerations involved in scoring Dovzhenko's work for contemporary audiences, while also reflecting on aspects of the premiere, in which the author performed as conductor and contributed to the coordination of the event.

The present score—one of the first by a non-Ukrainian composer to be widely presented with institutional support in the United States—follows a lineage of notable musical interpretations that have accompanied the film over time.

Historical Musical Interpretations of *Earth*

Since its release in 1930, *Earth* has had different musical scores starting with Ukrainian composer Levko Revutsky's accompaniment of the early screenings of the film. Sadly this brilliant work suffered from the intensely hostile political climate in the early 1930s that severely curtailed his compositional output and shifted his career focus to teaching.

Later reinterpretations include the orchestral score by Vyacheslav Ovchinnikov prepared for a restoration of the film in 1971 offering a more symphonic and emotionally expansive interpretation that has since become one of the most widely recognised musical versions. Finally a more recent soundtrack exists by the Ukrainian ensemble DakhaBrakha –an excellent fusion ethnic group- which didn't aim at scoring the film *stricto sensu*, but a free-style adaptation of their signature sound to the film.

TIFF and the Academy Museum of Motion Pictures

The origins of this project go back to June 2020 when I relocated to Kyiv, Ukraine, a chapter in my life which ended on account of the Russian invasion of 2022. In February and March of that year my recording studio on Pavliska Street was partly destroyed, and so my wife Kateryna and I decided to move back to the West.

At that time our mind was set to work on promoting Ukraine's cultural identity, or what little in fact existed of it (note: the heroic fight of Ukrainians for their survival can be said to run in parallel to the development of their own cultural consciousness). It was Kateryna who suggested I should start a new score for the Dovzhenko classic, an idea which immediately excited me.

Work began in the summer of 2022 and, thanks to her, interest arrived from the Toronto Film Festival and their film curator Dorota Lech who committed to screening the film with my new score as part of the TIFF events in support for Ukraine.

But before that could happen, the Academy Museum of Motion Pictures in Los Angeles, invited me to premiere and perform the score in person in Los Angeles in July 2023 which of course was accepted with great enthusiasm.

To me this project signifies much more than the music and its functionality on the screen, but an infinite pallet of emotions and memories that developed through two years of living in Ukraine and which came abruptly to an end in February of 2022 on account of a war with ramifications reaching as far back in time as the very events described in Dovzhenko's film.

1. Methodology: Practice-Based Film Music Research

This study follows a practice-based research methodology in which the act of composing the score functions as a form of analytical engagement with the film. Through the compositional process, close attention is given to the rhythm of montage, visual symbolism, narrative pacing, and emotional trajectory of the film. The resulting score therefore operates not only as an artistic work but also as an interpretative framework of our time, through which Dovzhenko's cinematic language can be examined.

2. Musical language and form

A study about a score for strings and piano for film such as this one, should start with a conversation about musical language and form even though music creation is instinctive, impulsive and ultimately mysterious especially to its own creator.

I am generally very sensitive to how a particular piece will be organised through time (form) and truly feel that this horizontal type of architecture, which is unique of music, is the very core of musical composition. In the Renaissance the Italians rightly started to use the word 'comporre' - to compose - for speaking about the act of music

Image 1

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creation. 'Comporre' is "riunire ordinatamente in un complesso." To gather; to put together in an orderly manner. 'To structure, then, along a horizontal, timely line of events'.

Structure - or form, as it is known in classical academia - puts the creator's intuition to the

Image 2

test, because, the forces that lead to improvise music in the first place can collide with the idea of order and structuring. In film scoring, my first step is always to improvise along the entire film over and over, sometimes for several days, and thus letting ideas come out unrestrained. I usually record all this material.

Throughout this early stage I prefer to think of nothing that might restrain my intuition and focus only on connecting with the energy of the film which by this time I would have watched several times in order to fully familiarise myself with it.

In this particular case, after one week of improvisational work, I had a vast amount of material and I realised I was comfortable with the idea of a piano concerto for the work. This gave me further enthusiasm to explore deeper into

the expressive possibilities of the keyboard and its interaction with the string ensemble.

It is at this point normally that the organisational part takes place. The composer becomes an architect and the structure begins to take shape (Here I cannot avoid quoting Goethe when he so magnificently defined architecture as '*erstarre Musik*', 'petrified music' ¹, a

¹ *Gespräche mit Goethe* by Eckermann, dated **23 March 1829**

definition which is closest to my experience also). Throughout the score, the piano - being the original improvisational vehicle of choice- leads the way in terms of output of ideas, and is also assigned most of the solo parts which adorn, here and there, the work. It is in

Image 3

some of these solo parts, especially during the scene where one of the Kulaks² attempts to sacrifice his own horse to prevent it from falling into the hands of the newly formed collectivised forces, that the most daring material for piano is presented.

But I would like to go back to the idea of structuring the improvisational material, before I move to further discuss this cue in the score.

Nowadays the process of ordering the improvisational material is heavily aided by the computer and the notation³ and/or DAW software. In the vast material left over from the improvisational stage, the composer selects, aided by intuition and his own instinct, the thematic material that can work best on the image. This process as I discuss later, is extremely challenging in silent film scoring because of the lack of input from the director.

The collaboration and dialogue between composer and director, in film scoring, is key to a successful outcome. There are many exceptions to this rule, and many instances where director proves to be clueless about music and stubbornly pushes the composer down a dead alley. But overall, as in most creative endeavours, collaboration and dialogue is key. The better and more skilful your team of collaborators is, the better the result of your work. Period.

² Kulak ('fist' in Russian) was initially a derogatory term used by Lenin to define the 'tight-fisted farmers resisting his policies. They became the target of brutal prosecution by the communist regime resulting in millions killed and/or deported. <https://history.hanover.edu/courses/excerpts/111stalin.html>

³ Credit is due to Steinberg and Dorico who have supported my work with their brilliant notation software

Once the thematic material is chosen, the selection is usually developed across the film, in order to create cohesion and musical discourse. As the thematic material originates from the improvisational material at the piano, then half of the work is done, as the source is already naturally cohesive. If the improvisational material is created from a range of different instruments or sources, then a completely different set of challenges appears. This was not the case in Zemlya.

3. Motivic material and development

Now back to the first example. In this short cue, chaos, despair and the violence that boils from the rage of the Kulak, are the inspiration for the rapid cascades of syncopated percussive keyboard notes, that frantically entangle the left and right hands. The harmonic language is broken, tonality lost, while coherence and balance are preserved only via a series of rhythmic motives that start on the left hand and quickly develop into faster units in the right hand. The original improvised material for this piece was a rather erratic banging of notes at the piano.

Image 4

During the improvisational stage I didn't focus at all on precision but on the unrestrained energy that I wanted to transfer to the keyboard in order to depict the emotions that the scene was giving me. It was only later that I meticulously edited note for note the entire piece to achieve a more defined architecture.

The overall direction of this thematic development is for the RH (right hand) to gravitate towards the higher register and the LH to fall in the opposite direction, suggesting the disintegration of reason and control that the characters are going through [image 1 - bars 297 and following].

This is one of the wildest moments in both the score and the film, and three different cues were composed until I found the material that gave me exactly what I wanted for such a dramatic scene.

I said this piece is atonal because overall the majority of the musical language of the score

The image shows a musical score for two instruments: Tub. B. (Tuba) and Pno. (Piano). The score begins at measure 1440. The Tub. B. part is written on a single staff with a treble clef. The Pno. part is written on two staves (treble and bass clefs). The piano part is marked with a forte dynamic (*ff*) and the tempo/style marking *solenne*. The music is atonal and features complex rhythmic patterns, including triplets and sixteenth notes. The score is presented in a standard musical notation format with various articulations and dynamics.

Image 5

is tonal and with a rather defined motivic architecture that guides the viewer's musical experience alongside the narrative development of the film.

Following Wagner, whose work has been a profound influence on me, I enjoyed creating a large-scale musical drama in which leitmotifs bind the ideas together. The poetic scenes of the fields, swept away by the hypnotic pulse of the gale [image 3], are shaped by their own motif; Basil's tragic fate is marked by another, first heard at the opening of the film [image 2] and later returning to define his darkest moment; and love, with its power to unite man and woman, is given its own theme, first appearing during the film's most romantic night and returning at the very end, when Basil's former girlfriend finds hope in the arms of another man [image 4].

One of the sections closest to my heart, both musically and cinematically, is the third act. From bar 1356 onwards, we witness the villagers finally embracing their destiny: becoming one with the state, accepting the abolition of private property, and yielding to collectivisation. Basil has been killed under the cover of darkness, and at the funeral his body is seen for the first time carried by a few strong hands. Yet the first image we are given of him is as though he were suspended in mid-air, with no visible trace of those bearing him below. In this way, Basil becomes one with the fields, one with the land [bar 1482], a perfect example of Dovzhenko's poetic cinema at work. Homa, his murderer—by

far the most compelling character in the film—gradually descends into madness [bar 1546], as the torment of having killed a man takes hold of him entirely.

T1 Desperate priest

The image shows a musical score for a scene titled 'Desperate priest'. It consists of five staves. The top staff is a grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The second staff is a bass clef staff with a 'ff' dynamic marking and the word 'intense' written above it. The third and fourth staves are grand staves. The fifth staff is a bass clef staff with a 'ff' dynamic marking and the word 'intense' written above it. The score features various musical notations including notes, rests, and dynamic markings.

Image 6

villagers, symbolising a dying, corrupt, and obsolete order; the arrival of a new leader for the people; and the famous nude shots of Basil's former girlfriend during her nervous breakdown—censored by the Soviet authorities at the time, but now included in the new version of the film ⁴.

This entire sequence is first introduced by a solemn theme that carries the full emotional weight of the film's dramatic resolution. It first appears at bar 1440 in the solo piano, then returns at bar 1474, and again at bar 1570, each time with renewed energy and dramatic force [image 5].

4. Dovzhenko's cinematic language through the lens of the composer

The following chapter requires been familiarised with the film as it delves into Dovzhenko's style and intentions in some key scenes. This information is however important to further understand the logic of film composer's mind at work.

Towards the end of Act 3, we enter the film's grandest and most epic section. This extended sequence intertwines several narrative threads: the villagers' journey towards a new ideological realm; Homa's descent into madness; the delivery of a newborn baby, as a metaphor for the birth of a new society; the priest's desperate plea to the Lord for vengeance upon the rebellious

⁴ <https://www.theguardian.com/film/filmblog/2013/nov/22/top-10-silent-movies-films>

Dovzhenko's complex and magnificently beautiful final sequence—perhaps one of the most profoundly poetic achievements of pre-war cinema—accomplishes something rather singular: it brings into confrontation some of the most mysterious forces of life itself with powerful editing decisions. Nothing is static, nothing is stable, and nothing will remain the same by the end of this section. A woman in labour finally gives birth; a grieving lover tears off her clothes, exposing her naked body, perhaps as a symbol of the profound loss of control at work; a once confident murderer (Homa, the kulak) is consumed by remorse and madness; the death of one leader gives way to the arrival of another; and earlier images of peacefully roaming animals are replaced by wild horses in stampede. The list could go on.

Image 7

What unfolds is a monumental display of opposing forces colliding with one another. Broadly speaking, these dynamics are:

1. Conflict between a rural and traditional society, with the new industrialised order
2. Juxtaposition of those who have (Kulaks) with those who want to have (collective)
3. Clash between a vision of a world that believes in god and a world without god
4. Juxtaposition of life and death, creation and distraction
5. Conflict between order and chaos
6. And finally, the juxtaposition between collective behaviour and the emotions and needs of the individual.

Basil, the unfortunate protagonist of the film, functions as a kind of catalyst. He carries a disruptive energy that seems perpetually to drive the action forward, unsettling events in unpredictable ways. He is, one might say quite simply, a troublemaker. I find little in him to inspire sympathy. I understand that my perception of this character is in great contrast with

the effect it might have had a century ago on the audience. He is driven neither by justice nor by necessity, but perhaps by greed or ambition.

The image shows a musical score for a piece titled "Beaten down father" on page 71. The score is written for a string quartet, with parts for Violin I, Violin II, Viola, and Cello/Double Bass. The music is in a minor key and features a complex, rhythmic melody in the Violin I part, often marked with triplets. The dynamics are marked as *mf* (mezzo-forte). The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, accents, and dynamic markings like *mf*, *nat.*, and *pizz.* (pizzicato).

Image 8

Basil can be read as a catalytic figure within the narrative, whose actions hasten the ideological transformation depicted in the film. Yet ideology here is little more than a pretext, a vehicle for the pursuit of deeper and more concealed desires. His father senses this, and it is for this reason that he is at first reluctant to join the son's revolt against the landowners. He will only do so when confronted with Basil's death.

All these energies finally resolve by dissolving into one another. With Basil dead and buried, and with the other rebellious figure—his

closest friend—assuming the role of leader within the village, Dovzhenko is prepared to bring us back to the apple groves and to the tender rain that blessed the fertile land in act one [image 2B]. After all the human drama, nature reclaims its harmonious cycle, at peace with itself and eternal.

3. Spotting the film and musical interpretation

In film terminology, the "spotting process" is the stage at which the composer determines the precise moments at which musical cues begin and end in relation to the film's visual structure.

In silent film, working without a director brings a series of challenges unique to this kind of scoring, and it requires discipline as well as a healthy dose of self-criticism. *Zemlya* was a

particularly challenging case, mostly because of Dovzhenko's editing style and rhythm, partly influenced by the Soviet school and partly guided by his own personal desire to create specific emotional and aesthetic impressions in the viewer.

There are parts of the film in which the passing of time since its release, as well as the changes in cinematic storytelling that have taken place over the last century, become especially evident. Finding the right solution for these passages was more difficult. One such area is the death of the grandfather at the beginning of the film, and later the section in which the father mourns the death of his son. Both passages considerably slow the pace of the film and challenge the rhythm and flow I had initially envisaged for the composition.

In the first of these sections, the solution came through the introduction of the harp as an extension of the orchestration [image 7], expressing the grandfather's peaceful spiritual connection to the very process of passing away, which Dovzhenko deliberately invites us to witness. Nature and its eternal self-generating forces, of which death is only one part, are beautifully conveyed through images of smiling babies, generous fruit trees in full bloom, and intercut shots of the indomitable wheat fields in the distance, elegantly brushed by the wind.

Here, the harp breaks away from the dominance of the string ensemble and piano. It creates space to think and feel. We think and feel according to the expression and bearing of the dying man, peacefully biting into an apple as he prepares for the end. Here, the function of the music is to accompany the action rather than interpret it.

Image 9

Later, following the murder of Basil—the haughty protagonist of the story—we are forced to observe the father’s piercing agony. Once again, Dovzhenko disrupts the pace of the film’s editing, forcing longer breaths: seconds expand into minutes, and it no longer seems to matter how long we watch this man suffer, his head sunk in his hands and hanging over the table like a dead body. The long shot repeats itself twice, almost exactly, in succession. This

Image 10

—beginning with a rather rustic shot of cows grazing— the entire section is extremely energetic and central to the message of the film, setting modernity against the old rural world and, more specifically, showing what is about to happen when the archaic world of tradition and custom collides with the indomitable mechanical energy of socialism. The tractor arrives in the village and, with it, vast possibilities, some more legitimate than others, as we later discover.

presented a distinctive challenge because, naturally, I wanted to build a degree of tension in this passage, both to underline the father’s despair and to prepare for the interruption brought by the priest’s arrival.

After giving it some thought, I decided to change the mood of the music in this sequence and opt for something resembling a wavering sense of numbness and despair, at once mesmerising in its stillness and deeply melancholic [image 8]. This approach helps to underline Dovzhenko’s desire to remain in that mood for as long as necessary, making each second feel like an eternity. Then, just as Opanas—the father—is interrupted by the dreaded knocking at the door, so too is the flow of the music abruptly broken.

Another challenge arose in the famous sequence showing the arrival of the tractor in the village for the first time. Here

The whole sequence is rather long, lasting just under ten minutes, and is dominated by a galloping piano pattern adorned with several demisemiquaver grace notes over a leap in pitch [image 9]. Dovzhenko divides the narrative of the sequence into two parts, with an epicentre marked by the breakdown of the tractor and the imaginative solution the villagers devise to repair it.

There are two key moments of sheer excitement that launch the energy of these two halves: the first occurs when the tractor is first spotted in the distance, and the second when it starts running again. Both moments of joy and exhilaration are underlined in the score by an electrifying piano glissando over a rising pizzicato pattern in the strings [image 10], further punctuated by arco stabs.

Here, two young villagers keep close watch on the events unfolding over the hill. They are like sentinels and informers of a sort for the rest of the village, who wait impatiently behind. These two youngsters hug, laugh, and wave their berets in the air, signalling the movement of the tractor. The time has come: a new era is arriving, embodied in the very presence of this mechanical artefact.

The entire sequence, from its opening—featuring four jolly cows ruminating—to the tractor finally halting in the village, is scored with thematic material structured in ternary-inspired form..

The tractor, the true protagonist of this sequence, with its mighty entry into the story and its momentary breakdown, keeps both the villagers and the viewer holding their breath. The excitement finally fades when the machine enters the village in triumph, trailing a great cloud of dust that engulfs both people and machine alike. And when the dust finally settles, it stands there, perfectly still, ready to be claimed by those with sufficient nerve and ambition. Basil's moment has finally arrived, his ambition now matched by the right tool, one he is fully prepared to exploit. Here, I once again chose to break the momentum of the preceding section by introducing a solo piano passage signalling the end of collective excitement and the time for the individual to act.

4. Tempo & synchronisation

An important consideration from the outset was to keep the music closely synchronised with the film. Maintaining a stable tempo throughout not only facilitates performance synchronisation but also reinforces the structural coherence between musical form and cinematic rhythm.

While scoring another Ukrainian silent film *The Night Coachman* (Tasin, 1929), I kept the tempo constant throughout, using divisions of the metre to achieve the greatest possible precision in synchronisation. This approach greatly simplifies the task of conducting the score live, especially in a work that contains numerous changes of metre. In the end, the score featured more than two hundred and fifty metre changes, all within a single tempo of 74 bpm.

The image shows a page of a musical score. At the top left, there is a box containing the letter 'Y' and the text 'Father is working in the fields'. At the top right, the number '55' is printed. The score consists of two staves. The upper staff is for a string instrument, with a treble clef and a key signature of one flat (B-flat). The lower staff is for a piano, with a bass clef and a key signature of one flat. The music is written in 4/4 time. The score begins with a dynamic marking of 'f' (forte). The piano part features several triplet markings. The score ends with a double bar line and a final 4/4 time signature.

Image 11

Between scenes, a buffer of two or three silent bars provides a safety margin in the event of a loss of synchronisation during performance, allowing a certain degree of flexibility for the conductor and the performers.

There is one particular moment in *Zemlya* that is especially challenging, in which the pulse of the score freezes completely and, for the brief span of five bars, rhythm itself seems to disappear. This section was initially improvised *ad libitum* at the piano, and it took several revisions of the notation before I achieved what I wanted [image 11].

At the end of this single 3/8 bar, the strings return to the pulse. The piano remains silent for one bar and then rejoins the ensemble. This is the most demanding passage in the score. All of this occurs in the middle of a distinctly propagandistic montage, one that reminds the viewer of the supposed marvels of Soviet mechanisation and life. The idea here was to have fun with the music and to reflect the joy the farmers display on screen. This brief piano passage also serves as the epicentre of the montage, mirroring the surrounding material through variation and extension.

Throughout this section, we see conveyor belts working energetically, happy peasants ploughing the land, Basil's new tractor labouring incessantly, and cheerful young women harvesting wheat. Ironically, only two years later Stalin would impose a catastrophic famine on these very people, causing the deaths of millions through starvation.

Here I sense a certain similarity with a different passage in Act 3, when the score again enters a solo piano section, signalling a new chapter in the story. The musical energy reaches its peak at bar 1524 [image 6], in the middle of the final sequence, and finds repose at bar 1599, when Basil's best friend assumes ideological control of the village. The musical material then becomes suddenly soft and mellow, and so too does this new reality: free from the hardship of manual labour and free from injustice.

A new and gentler order seems to begin, or at least such is the promise.

4. Modern music in silent cinema

For anyone interested in film scoring, silent cinema constitutes a particularly compelling field of practice. On the one hand, it offers numerous cautionary examples of inadequate scoring, produced by composers who regard these films as an opportunity to impose their own musical language with minimal supervision, often in the hope of benefiting from the prestige attached to canonical works of early cinema. On the other hand, silent film scoring provides rare scope for genuinely fresh musical material—something that has become increasingly scarce in contemporary film and television—while also enabling the composer to revive works that have, in some cases, receded into neglect.

In certain instances, composers choose to approach silent film through experimental means, whether by improvising live with electronics, piano, orchestra, or other instrumental forces. The results may or may not be persuasive, but the medium itself tends to invite a degree of aesthetic permissiveness. More generally, silent cinema is still often perceived as a flawed form: poorly preserved, dramatically exaggerated, technically primitive, and lacking the expressive subtlety of sound film. Some of these assumptions are, admittedly, justified in particular cases. Yet there also exists a smaller body of silent films that demands a far more nuanced and respectful treatment.

Silent cinema offers composers an unusually powerful role in articulating the latent dimensions of a film's narrative. In sound film, the presence of dialogue inevitably changes the function of music, binding it more closely to dramatic action and textual meaning. In silent cinema, however, music acquires an additional interpretative energy. In films with dialogue, a score may deepen subtext, intensify atmosphere, or supplement emotional meaning, but it cannot fundamentally redefine the narrative without working against the film itself. In silent cinema, by contrast, music possesses a far greater capacity to shape

perception. It can inflect tone, redirect emphasis, and in some cases even alter the apparent genre of a film, making a horror film seem comic, or a comedy appear melancholic.

Unfortunately, scores that truly do justice to the finest silent films remain relatively rare. One of my earliest exercises after leaving college was to score Murnau's *Nosferatu*. I quickly realised how easy it was to betray the essence of the film by treating it merely as a visual framework for musical invention, thereby reducing it to the status of an extended music video. Yet the opposite danger was equally real: an overly restrained score might fail to provide sufficient interpretative richness or expressive substance to sustain the experience fully, especially with the absence of dialogue.

What is required, therefore, is a careful balance between these extremes. The score must be sufficiently rich, detailed, and responsive to animate the images and illuminate the narrative, yet never so insistent as to overwhelm the film's own logic. Composers such as Carl Davis and Philip Glass, among others, have demonstrated exceptional mastery in this regard, and their work stand among the highest achievements in the field.

5. Conclusion

Dovzhenko was a brilliant and, at times, controversial filmmaker whose work has been both heavily labelled and repeatedly subjected to political and ideological scrutiny. In spite of the immense difficulties of filming during one of the most turbulent political periods in modern history, he managed to leave behind a substantial body of work, of which *Zemlya (Earth)* is undoubtedly the crown jewel.

The composition of my new musical score for *Earth* demonstrates how contemporary compositional practice can contribute to the renewed interpretation of silent cinema classics and in part their historical context, which, in my view, can revitalise our understanding of and interest in these works. Through a practice-based research approach, the composer can open the door to a closer examination of the director's montage structure, visual symbolism, narrative pacing, and ideological message.

My work does not aim to replace earlier musical interpretations, but rather to participate in the evolving performance history of the film. By addressing through music the challenges posed by the rhythmic logic of the editing, the poetic treatment of landscape, and the

deliberate high contrast embedded in the narrative, the score seeks to present *Earth* in a light more attentive to the historical knowledge we now possess, almost a century after the events it reflects.

Image 12: The author during the premiere of the score at the Motion Picture Academy Museum, July 2023

As I take this work on the road and use it to reach new audiences, drawing fresh admirers into the enchanting world of silent cinema, I continue to observe audience reactions with fascination. The public connects with this film remarkably well, often in ways that feel vastly different from, and perhaps more powerful than, their responses to many modern productions.

And then a different kind of question begins to form in my mind: why do we still respond so strongly to films such as *Zemlya*, while seeming increasingly incapable of creating works with the same degree of magnetism and cinematic wonder?

Hegel famously wrote in the preface to *Elements of the Philosophy of Right* that "philosophy is its own time comprehended in thought⁵." One might extend this idea to cinema by suggesting that film, perhaps more than any other art form, becomes its own

⁵ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365954243_PHILOSOPHY_IS_ITS_OWN_TIME_COMPREHENDED_IN_THOUGHT_ON_THE_NORMATIVITY_OF_HEGEL'S_PRACTICAL_PHILOSOPHY

time comprehended in images. If this is so, then we are inevitably bound by the circumstances of our own historical moment: our creative work reflects the spirit of our age just as profoundly as Dovzhenko's films reflect the tensions and aspirations of his.

Perhaps, then, we might conclude by observing that ours is, above all, an age of observers. We live surrounded by an extraordinary abundance of cultural production and information, unprecedented in scale and accessibility. Then a second question comes to the fore, not whether new great material can be produced, but how we choose to devote our attention to any of it, old or new.

My hope is that part of our attention will continue to be directed towards the enduring works of cinema's past—towards masterpieces such as *Zemlya*—whose power to inspire reflection and artistic renewal remains undiminished.

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